

**BEYOND ALL INCLUSIVE:
AN EXPLORATION OF RESORT HOTEL GUESTS'
PERCEIVED VALUE OF "ULTRA ALL-INCLUSIVE"
PACKAGE ADDITIONS**

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the perceived value of “Ultra All-Inclusive” (Ultra AI) resort package inclusions and their influence on guests’ willingness to accept a higher price (WTA). A two-stage approach was employed. First, exploratory research established the current norms of Ultra AI packages through analysis of over 400 online descriptions and performance insights using content analysis of Tripadvisor’s “Top 25” AI hotels. Second, a survey of 141 guests in AI resorts in Rhodes, Greece, measured perceived value for 52 package inclusions.

The findings highlight the dominance of Food & Beverage (F&B) offerings in driving both satisfaction and positive electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM), while revealing a high implied willingness-to-pay for uncommon but emerging inclusions such as Dine-out experiences, spa sessions, no check in/out times and at least one included excursion. Suggested innovations emerging from guest responses signal opportunities for further development of the Ultra AI model.

The study contributes to the limited literature on Ultra AI tourism by synthesizing stated guest value with revealed performance indicators, offering actionable insights for resort managers and hoteliers.

Keywords: All-Inclusive, Ultra All-Inclusive, Resort Tourism, Willingness to Pay, Hospitality Management, Tourism Marketing

INTRODUCTION

As tourists' preferences are constantly evolving, AI (All-Inclusive) holidays have inarguably emerged as a leading travel choice in many sun, sea and sand destinations (Anderson, 2010; Ozturk et al., 2017). In fact, 61% of UK outgoing package holidays sold in 2018 were all-inclusive holidays (De Vries, 2019). The popularity of the concept, attributed to the numerous benefits it offers key stakeholders (Farmaki et al., 2017), along with the rapid growth of the tourism sector in general, has brought an increase in AI accommodation capacity but also in competition (Bilgili et al., 2016; Pai & Ananthakumar, 2017). However, a limited understanding exists around how much hospitality and tourism providers know about AI customer preferences so that they can tailor their offerings and differentiate from competitors (Rayna & Striukova, 2009; Kucukusta, 2017).

Despite AI' growing popularity as a form of holidays, a widespread perception that the AI concept does not appeal to high spenders has been prevalent amongst travellers until recent years (Roris, 2009; Crocker, 2017). While these associations were possibly portrayed due to earlier and more mass-oriented forms of AI, which indeed suffered in overall service quality (Ayik et al., 2013), AI Resorts have improved their level of service dramatically and have become much more sophisticated (TTG, 2010a; Levine, 2014). Demand for high-end AI holidays has risen considerably (Pike, 2012) and has attracted wealthier travellers, as reflected upon international hotel chains that have invested into this new high-end form of all-inclusive holidays, most commonly referred to as "Ultra" All-Inclusive (Corona, 2014, Haydock, 2016). However, the range of services and activities that Ultra AI resorts offer varies vastly, without any standardization in what the term signifies in terms of included food, beverages and activities or services available without extra charge in such resorts (Rayna & Striukova, 2014).

An important success factor of the AI business model is attributed to the fact that it provides resorts with the operational efficiency needed to offer packages perceived as better

value (Roris, 2009). The introduction of AI to the luxury segment seems logical, considering that even though luxury travellers are not principally driven by cost, most are undeniably still driven by value (Hallot, 2013).

Current wisdom on the AI business model suggests that its cost benefits derive mainly from: a) lower transaction costs, b) economies of scale c) a greater use of fixed cost assets, d) better forecast accuracy and consequently, e) better staff and inventory management (Rayna & Striukova, 2009; Roris, 2009). Further to these cost benefits, seasonal all-inclusive resorts seem to enjoy an extended period of operation compared to non-AI resorts (Bilgili et al. 2016; Menekse, 2005), higher occupancy rates, longer average stay (Ozdemir et al., 2012; Roris, 2009; Gökdeniz et al., 2000) and better accuracy of profit calculation (Farmaki et al., 2017). Rayna & Striukova imply an apparent contradiction that “*offering more actually costs less*” (2009, p.366) to explain how Ultra AI resorts have managed to compete with both traditional AI and non-AI luxury resorts. Ultra AI resorts in particular, seem to further benefit from turning the cost trade-off into a time trade-off in offerings (e.g. ten restaurants available for dinner during a five night stay) but also by the existence of a myopic behavior on behalf of guests, who appear to reduce consumption when sensing abundance, in contrast to increasing it when sensing a scarcity of offerings (Gupta & Gentry, 2016; Rayna & Striukova, 2009). Indeed, evidence shows that resorts which embraced the AI business model seem to have enjoyed higher profitability margins than traditional resorts (Ciftci et al., 2007), while early Ultra AI adopters have been able to benefit from the combination of cost leadership with product differentiation (Rayna & Striukova, 2009).

Although the AI travel mode has recently attracted more attention, academic research so far has focused on the effects of the model on destinations and tourists’ satisfaction (Ozdemir et al., 2012; Cetinsoz & Artuger, 2014; Erul & Woosnam, 2016). Furthermore, while there are numerous studies on hotel attributes and their effect on travelers’ willingness to pay (Dolnicar & Otter, 2003; Masiero et al., 2015), there seems to be a lack of such insights focusing on the

key elements of Standard and Ultra AI hotel packages. On the other hand, many pioneering hotel elements such as technological or service innovations have a short period of adoption by competition, after which they rapidly become expected by guests (Kim et al., 2017). This issue highlights the importance of continuously assessing customer preferences and expectations thus allowing hotel owners and tour operators to design packages centered around customer needs (Pai & Ananthakumar, 2017).

The purpose of this work is to provide a preliminary understanding of current industry practices concerning elements included in AI and Ultra AI resorts through a two-stage approach. Given the lack of research regarding guest preferences specifically for AI resorts, the literature on the broader topic was first examined to understand approaches adopted by previous research and inform the methodology of this study. For the same reason, the first phase of Stage 1 was exploratory in nature, attempting to differentiate between elements that are considered standard inclusions in AI resorts from ones that are beyond these basic AI offerings.

Furthermore, an analysis of reviews of the twenty-five leading all-inclusive hotels on Tripadvisor.com was performed in the second phase of Stage 1, aiming to account for important performance elements which contribute in positive e-word-of-mouth. The authors projected that the recency of the Tripadvisor list, formulated by current consumer expectations, would offer a valuable indication of resorts currently offering an pleasing form of All-Inclusive.

In stage 2, after identifying elements beyond those typically included in traditional AI resorts the study goes on to measure AI travelers' perceived value. In specific, the findings reveal that some of these Ultra AI offerings may increase guests' willingness to pay (WTP) for a higher priced resort, which includes these offerings in its package. We then synthesize the results of stated WTP and stated value of each offering with the results of the TripAdvisor content analysis, to arrive at conclusions that account for both attitudinal and performance

dimensions into measurement of perceived value.

By examining guests' preferences, measuring WTP for current Ultra AI resort offerings and synthesizing the research findings of all methods, the research conclusions should assist hotel managers in designing or improving AI packages by focusing on elements which AI guests perceive as most valuable. Keeping in mind that value for money is of utmost importance for travelers (Roris, 2009), hotel managers may use the information to target spend on inclusions which bring added value, while excluding unnecessary offerings that increase their cost without correspondingly contributing in demand. Moreover, the study reveals items desired by guests beyond the list of identified offerings, thus providing opportunities to further enhance hotels following this business model.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Defining the new all-inclusive

While a few years ago the AI market was a small niche, it's now becoming "more mainstream" (Crocker, p. 2, 2017). Indeed, while budget used to be a main driver for all-inclusives in the past, it seems that upscale and wealthy travellers are becoming equally attracted to the convenience of the model (Friedland, 2013). Traditionally, the standard all-inclusive form of travel represents a combination of various tourism goods and services, marketed and sold as one inclusive package (Middleton, 1994). In its most basic form, the all-inclusive resort has been defined as an establishment that offers accommodation, meals, drinks and activities for a fixed priced (Rayna & Striukova, 2009; T.Lopez-Guzman et al., 2016), often sold as part of an all-inclusive package tour which also includes transport and service charges (Turner & Troiana, 1987).

Previous studies have identified several important factors for choosing all-inclusive holidays. Certain core characteristics of AI packages such as convenience and cost have long been recognised as significant motivators in tourism literature (Touche Ross, 1975; Sheldon

& Mak, 1987; Heung & Chu, 2000; Anderson et al., 2009) along with personal safety and the general sense of safety they offer (Enoch, 1996; Wickens, 2002; Issa & Jayawardena, 2003; Wong & Kwong, 2004, Roris, 2009). The easiness of social contact AI holidays offer, favorable recommendations from friends, elimination of surprises and unexpected costs and the availability of specialised activities for children and adults are also factors that favour the choice of AI travel (Wong & Kwong, 2004; Tavares & Kozak, 2015; Ozturk et al., 2017; Pai & Ananthakumar, 2017). While not negligent, Wong & Kwong (2004) show that sport facilities and the destination's distance from their departure location are less important considerations in the choice of travel mode.

Although there is still a stigma of mediocre quality attached to such packages (Crocker, 2017), all-inclusive resorts have responded to the increasing popularity and competition by upmarketing their provision of services (Farmaki et al., 2017), from luxurious accommodation and a larger range of experiential activities to providing multiple and finer-dining options (Levine, 2014; D'Amico, 2015). Due to the great variation in the elements offered between AI hotels (Ozdemir et al., 2012) as well as the negative connotation attached to AI resorts, many resorts tried to specify their differentiation when marketing their package, using terms such as "Luxury included" and "Gourmet included" (Pike, 2012, p.12).

As upper scale and more inclusive hotels gained popularity in the market, a new standard of all-inclusive was established, commonly referred to as Ultra All-Inclusive (Rayna & Striukova, 2009; Corona, 2014; Ikkos, 2014), sometimes also mentioned as Super all-inclusive (Issa & Jayawardena, 2003), Mega all-inclusive, All-Inclusive Plus, High class all-inclusive (Çiftçi, 2007), Luxury, Premium (Roris, 2009; Ryall, 2015) or Imperial All-Inclusive (Gomes & Pereira, 2016) and "All-Inclusive 2.0" (Agadoni, 2017).

Unlike most standard AI resorts which offer a limited selection of local drinks (Corona, 2014), the range of drinks in these resorts typically includes free Premium or at least International branded spirits (TTG, 2010a; Ikkos, 2014) while the dining experience includes

a range of gourmet a la carte restaurants beyond the usual buffet outlets (Pike, 2012; Corona, 2014). Ultra AI resorts are typically 24hour all-inclusives and amongst other extras are expected to include room service, daily re-stocked in room mini-bars and unlimited access to a larger number of facilities than those offered at standard AI resorts (Rayna & Striukova, 2009; TTG, 2010b; Corona, 2014).

1.2 Hotel selection determinants – Approaches and framework

Prior studies suggest that the quality of the hotel in an AI package choice appears of great significance regardless of the tourist's standards and was found more important than destination's attributes such as its natural attractiveness, culture and history (Ayik et al., 2013). In line with these insights, evidence from Scandinavian tour operators show that the destination appears a secondary consideration for those creating and selling travel packages (Wall-Reinius et al., 2021). Similar results were yielded by Pai & Ananthakumar (2017), who also included travel attributes, such as length of stay and season of travel in their study. By knowing which hotel attributes matter to guests, hotel owners and managers can effectively tailor their facilities and services to attract more guests, upsell rooms and products and increase satisfaction (Lockyer, 2005; Masiero et al., 2015; Hamilton et al., 2017). While certain attributes such as larger rooms and free services are almost universally desirable and easier to predict (Masiero et al., 2015), other preferences differ among diverse segments consumer groups (Zhang et al., 2011; Kucukusta 2017). Moreover, since customers have stepped up their expectations, hotels need to incorporate new emerging attributes to maintain or increase their market share in the ultra AI market (Kim et al., 2017).

Although attribute preferences and hotel selection theory have attracted ample attention in literature, knowledge in this emerging field seems to be fragmented and incomplete in terms of the importance of ultra AI attributes measured, its appeal to different market segments, leading to a low extent of consent amongst researchers regarding the most important hotel attributes (Dolnicar & Otter, 2003). Moreover, many existing studies regarding hotel selection

purchasing criteria are criticized for exhibiting false assumptions and flawed methodology (Jones & Chen, 2011)., as will be elaborated further in this subsection.

In a paper reviewing twenty-one empirical studies between 1984 and 2000, Dolnicar & Otter (2003) identified 173 hotel attributes measured, which were categorised into ten areas, namely *Services, Hotel, Location, Room, Price/Value, F&B (Food & Beverages), Image, Security, Marketing* and *Others*. A summary of categorization of attributes used in selected literature, which varies between studies, is presented in Table 1. Each of the research selected in Table 1 has been well cited by subsequent studies and all included a review of other relevant preceding literature.

Table 1: Hotel/Resort categorization of attributes in selected literature

Clow et al. (1994)	Callan (1998)	Dolnicar & Otter (2003)	Lockyer (2005)	Wen (2012)	Kim et al. (2017)
Price	Price/value	Price/value	Price	Price	Value
Location	Location	Location	Location	Location	Location
Physical appearance	Image	Image	Cleanliness	Appearance	Cleanliness
Quality & Dependability of service	Tangibles-bedrooms	Room	Facilities	Accommodation	Room
Reputation & name familiarity	Tangibles-other	Hotel Services	Other	Quality	Service
Security	Competence	Marketing		Efficiency	
	Access	F&B		Reputation	
	Additional services	Security		F&B	
	Leisure facilities	Other		Facilities & Programs	
	Security				
	Service provided				

The individual items most frequently included in the studies reviewed by Dolnicar & Otter (2003) were *friendliness of staff, price, service quality, cleanliness of room, location, room service* and *bed comfort*. Although these studies differed in methodology and target groups and produced inconsistent findings, the criterion most frequently identified as most important in studies between 1984 and 2000 was convenience of Location, followed by Service Quality, Reputation and Friendliness of staff (ibid.). Interestingly, in more recent literature specifically regarding the AI holidays and the perspective of the tour operator, hotel location was found not be a major consideration (Wall-Reinius et al., 2021)

While most studies during this period were focused on pre-purchase selection (Wen, 2012), the majority of them fail to distinguish between pre and post-purchase criteria, asking respondents to mark the importance of attributes that cannot be evaluated unless they have already visited the hotel (Jones & Chen, 2011). For example, several studies (e.g Lockyer, 2005; Zhang et al., 2011; Sohrabi et al., 2012; Caber & Albayrak, 2014), confuse initial choice with repeat purchase and include factors such as bed comfort, cleanliness or politeness of staff in measurement of hotel selection criteria. The knowledge of important factors is useful for the industry, however, if assumed travelers have access to this information before arrival, the effect on hotel selection is most likely indirect. Therefore, to overcome this imitation of prior research we accommodate the effect of sources such as “online reviews” or “reputation”.

Although a larger amount of hotel attribute research between 2000 and 2011 was concerned with satisfaction and return intention (Wen, 2012), many of these studies still suffered flaws and limitations. According to Jones and Chen (2011), many studies inaccurately assume that factors which are rated as most important are also determining factors for a hotel choice. Indeed, certain attributes such as security are likely to be desired by most travelers, although they are not adequate criteria for selecting a hotel (Masiero et al.,

2015; Kim et al., 2017). For the majority of hotels, even core attributes such as location and hotel rooms cannot be relied on anymore to increase profitability (Ottenbacher & Gnoth, 2005; Kim et al., 2017), a finding that highlights the necessity for All-Inclusive hotels to form packages which keep up with today's demanding guest preferences.

More recent literature concerning hotel attributes can be distinguished in terms of its focus between studies concerned with the effect of hotel attributes on a) customer attitude and behaviour and b) hotel performance (Kim et al., 2017). Recent studies have included attributes such as availability of wifi and express or online check in/out (Schamel, 2012; Hamilton et al., 2017), level of green practices (Millar & Baloglu, 2011; Kim et al., 2017) and online ratings (Hudson & Thal., 2013), all of which have been found capable of affecting customer behavior towards visiting, returning or recommending a hotel.

Jones & Chen's study (2011) is one of the few studies that advances a two-stage process of online hotel selection recognizing that evaluative criteria differ from choice criteria. For example, while in an initial selection of hotels for consideration "availability of swimming pool" was an important filter, different criteria such as "reviews" and "price" were used to narrow the hotel down into a smaller choice set (ibid.). The authors also highlighted the danger of measurement error when solely relying on predetermined factors of importance for hotel attributes as a) important factors may be left out and ignored and b) other factors are ranked which although respondents may consider important, may not have crossed their minds during the decision process. This can be easier understood taking as example a study by Alabi et al. (2013) regarding factors affecting room demand and price, in which "availability of fire extinguisher" was found to be the most important attribute, while "good fire detection system" was ranked higher than value for money.

Another important shortcoming of work in this stream is the lack of trade-off constraints in the measurement of importance for hotel selection and hotel amenity preferences (Kucukusta, 2017). For example, when respondents are asked to describe their room of preference a large

suite is usually preferable, however when it comes to paying a price premium many would settle for a smaller room (Dolnicar & Otter, 2003).

2. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to map the elements currently included in Ultra AI Resorts beyond the standard All-Inclusive package inclusions and assess their relative value for the All-Inclusive traveler’s experience. To meet these objectives, a two-stage approach was adopted. The first stage was exploratory in nature and aimed to identify the idiosyncratic features of Ultra AI resorts and distinguish them from the standard AI concept. Leading Ultra AI hotels were then further examined in pursue of package features associated with guest satisfaction. The second stage of the research consisted of administering a survey to AI hotel guests on the island of Rhodes, Greece. Findings were triangulated in combination with results of content analysis of leading hotel’s reviews on TripAdvisor, as depicted in Figure 1. The content was retrieved from reviews of Tripadvisor’s “Top 25” rankings, as they stood during the period that the survey was administered to hotel guests.

Insert figure 1 here

As the tourism literature advocates, hotel selection decision is a multi-dimensional and complex task (Lockyer, 2005) and lacks a widely-endorsed measurement instrument (Jones & Chen, 2011). This study focused on measuring the perceived value of each attribute and its effect on guests' WTP a higher price for the resort, rather than the actual effect on hotel selection.

2.1 Stage 1: Exploratory Research and Content Analysis

The initial phase of this stage involved the collection and analysis of secondary data. To establish the current norms for Standard and Ultra all-inclusive resorts, All-inclusive descriptions of over 400 hotels worldwide were studied, through individual and hotel chain websites, online booking portals, tour operators' online brochures as well as the author's on-site visits to AI resorts. In addition to the above, the study included hotels selected from most-popular and highest-ranked listings on four online travel and guest review platforms, Tripadvisor.com, Holidaycheck, Booking.com and Expedia, all considered reliable, direct and recent sources of information (Rodríguez-Díaz and Espino-Rodríguez, 2018).

Furthermore, as a large and international source of independent travelers' ratings (Zhang et al., 2011) Tripadvisor.com website was used to further examine the top twenty-five All-Inclusive hotels internationally as announced in January 2019. Elements of these top-performing resort's AI packages were identified and included in the questionnaire subsequently developed. Most importantly, whilst most previous studies on hotel attributes seem to have either focused on guest opinions or hotel performance without combining both aspects (Kim et al., 2017), the use of Tripadvisor.com's top twenty-five ranking ensured a "performance" dimension was also taken into consideration in this study.

Since exceeding customer expectations has been recognized as a main driver of online reviews, (Serra-Cantallops et al., 2018) the initial analysis of this dataset aimed to identify recurring elements that potentially surpass customer expectations and increase their positive online word-of-mouth. The analysis was performed by gathering the top "trending" words or

phrases appearing in reviews of each of the top twenty-five hotels on Tripadvisor.com. Since Tripadvisor.com lists the seventeen “trending” words of each hotels’ reviews, these seventeen words or phrases most commonly used for each of the hotels produced 425 words/phrases which were grouped and measured for frequency with the help of statistical software (SPSS). Based on the items which appeared as most referred to the items were grouped into thirteen broader categories, as following:

- Room type
- Entertainment or Activity
- Food & Beverage
- Design feature
- Service feature or amenity
- Location
- Staff
- Environmental feature
- Facility
- Holiday description
- Room feature or amenity
- Various Other
- Excursion

Validation was sought for the grouping through multiple moderators in order to account for several individual perspectives all of which yielded the same categories with similar wording, as has also been used in a large number of previous research on hotel attributes. Out of the top-25 hotels on Tripadvisor.com two hotels were omitted as they had very few reviews in English, which is currently the only language for which Tripadvisor.com presents the most frequently appearing phrases. Instead, one extra hotel was added, which was recommended by the tour operator executives used to pre-test to the questionnaire items, as explained in the next section. Almost all items were used with a positive connotation, however four recurring phrases which were tied to a negative element of one of the hotels were identified and removed from the analysis.

2.2 Stage 2: Survey Design

The survey included was intended to measure the various package elements of Ultra AI Resorts that emerged from the previous stage and exclude items that appeared to have become the norm for Standard AI hotels (e.g. free-wifi or the possibility of dining in one additional restaurant). Since respondents were asked to indicate perceived value of “additional” inclusions, care was taken to examine the AI descriptions of participating hotels before the questionnaires were distributed to guests. Moreover, the exclusion of these attributes assisted in reducing the questionnaire length to reduce participants’ cognitive load and increase response rate.

Methodological flaws identified in previous studies were taken into consideration during construction of the questionnaire to avoid undermining the validity of the results. Since the close-ended questions of the survey focused on travelers’ *pre-purchase evaluation* of additional inclusions, items which could not be directly assessed before arrival were not included, although items tied to an “inclusion” of marketing value were measured. For example, “quality of food” was not an included item, though guests were asked to rate their perceived value for “Michelin starred chefs running the hotel restaurants”. As mentioned, the questionnaire focused on the package elements of All-Inclusive resorts, therefore items not directly related to the AI program such as location or physical appearance were not included in the questionnaire, apart from two extensively researched items, “king sized bed” and “pillow menu”, which were included to provide linkage between this study’s findings with previous or future studies of similar scope.

Demographic profile

A usable sample of 141 responses was gathered drawing on guests from AI resorts in Rhodes, Greece. To ensure eligibility for inclusion, we have set some screening criteria. The sample excluded anyone under the age of 18 but included respondents aged over 65 years, as this is considered an important market segment for All-Inclusive travel (Ozturk et al., 2017),

expected to further develop in the near future (Caber & Albaryak, 2014). The questionnaires were placed in hotel rooms two days after guests' arrival as well as on transfer coaches of guests departing from 4* and 5* AI hotels, after their stay. The demographic background of the respondents is presented below. The instruments were designed in English and all responses were in English, comprising of several nationalities, as presented in Appendix 1. The initial questions of this survey consisted of personal (age, nationality, gender) and travel characteristics (if accompanied by children), as previous studies imply that differences exist in travel preferences, expenditure and price sensitivity between various demographic groups and travel circumstances (Anderson, 2010, Kucukusta, 2017).

Question Format

To account for the price trade-off which occurs when more services are added into a package, respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they would be prepared to pay a higher cost for each element, rather than simply rate the importance of each attribute on their purchase decision.

On the other hand, as argued by Desmet (2016), directly asking respondents to assign a monetary value of their "Willingness To Pay" (WTP) or "Willingness To Accept" (WTA) can be cognitively challenging. After distributing a preliminary questionnaire to a small group of respondents, a *numerical rating scale* of value rather than a monetary indication was used as this seemed to produce more fully completed surveys. In fact, although knowledge of a valid WTP (or WTA) is extremely valuable for developing optimal pricing strategies (Breidert et al., 2006), according to Nessim & Dodge (1995), even if guests rate this truthfully, their real purchasing behavior may be different. Considering the above, for items 1 to 52 respondents were asked to rate their WTA in a proactive statement, as following: *"When selecting and booking an all-inclusive resort, I would be willing to accept a higher price for the same All Inclusive package, if the below attribute/service was also included/provided:"* A seven-point Likert scale (1-"Extremely Unlikely" to 7-"Extremely Likely") was used for all items, based

on previous studies measuring the value of hotel attributes and amenities. No distinction between the terms Ultra and Standard AI attributes and this stage was necessary and the general term “All Inclusive package” was preferred to avoid any confusion.

Survey Items

Due to the discussed apparent lack of previous studies regarding Ultra AI attributes, the questionnaire’s items were grouped based on categories used in studies determining travel preferences of general AI features with the exclusion of non-relevant dimensions. The attributes included were identified in this study’s secondary research as important additions by Ultra AI resorts, although the individual value of each item has not been established in tourism literature.

Following the list of 52 items, respondents were asked to choose the three most strongly valued items from the list, which were the only three for which a direct monetary indication of “WTA” was then asked for. It was considered by the author that these responses would provide an adequate indication of relative value while avoiding “questionnaire fatigue”. For the same reason a price of 100 euro per night was chosen as a reference point, which actually also appeared not to be far off the average room night cost during the period the questionnaires were handed out (April/May). An open-ended question concerning elements which may have not been mentioned in the questionnaire but guests would be willing to pay for in their package, concluded the questionnaire.

Reliability - Validity

Although the study concentrated on the value of each individual item, the broader categories of these were tested for reliability, producing the results illustrated on Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

	Transfer Services	SPA, Beauty & Weddings	Communication Services	Various	Food & Beverage	Activities Entertainment	Personalised Services	Room Items
Inter-Item Correlation								
Transfer Services	1	0,616	0,534	0,738	0,706	0,634	0,576	0,699
SPA, Beauty & Weddings	0,616	1	0,646	0,721	0,656	0,662	0,589	0,671
Communication Services	0,534	0,646	1	0,688	0,591	0,539	0,558	0,598
Various	0,738	0,721	0,688	1	0,743	0,636	0,632	0,727
Food & Beverage Items	0,706	0,656	0,591	0,743	1	0,819	0,745	0,759
Activities / Entertainment	0,634	0,662	0,539	0,636	0,819	1	0,819	0,649
Personalised Services	0,576	0,589	0,558	0,632	0,745	0,819	1	0,654
Room Items	0,699	0,671	0,598	0,727	0,759	0,649	0,654	1
Cronbach's Alpha (CA)	0,851	0,888	0,909	0,894	0,946	0,933	0,693	0,859
CA if item* deleted							0,713	
*babysitting service by certified staff								

The exposure of the survey to the *expert opinion* of tour operator contract and product managers for the provision of face and content validity resulted in slight changes to the list of items, in order to accurately capture distinguishing Ultra AI package inclusions beyond those of typical AI's. The survey wording and scale were changed after pilot testing to address its predictive validity. In addition, to achieve higher reliability of the results findings an “alternative form” of question was included, by asking respondents to additionally state the three most valued items from the list of attributes they had ranked.

Establishing Norms

For the measurement of WTA a higher supplement, a mean score of 4,00 or above was considered of high potential impact, a score between 3,70 and 4 ,00 of somewhat high while items with mean scores lower than 3,70 were considered to carry somewhat low potential impact. Regarding the items selected in the respondents “three most-valued inclusions”, items with 10 or more mentions were considered to carry both high added value and distinguishing power, items with 4 to 9 mentions were considered somewhat high, while items with less than 4 appearances were considered to carry either somewhat low added value or low distinguishing power.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Stage 1 Results

The first part of the research analysed the 17 most frequently appearing words or phrases in reviews of each of the top 25 All-Inclusive hotels in the world for 2019, as appeared on Tripadvisor.com. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3, grouped into the categories each phrase referred to:

Table 3 : Categories of most frequently used phrases in Tripadvisor.com's top 25 AI hotels' reviews

Phrase Category	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Additional Restaurant outlets	61	17,5	17,5
Room type or description	36	10,3	27,9
Bar (day and evening)	29	8,3	36,2
Pool or Waterslide Facilities	21	6,0	42,2
Main (buffet) Restaurant	18	5,2	47,4
Food, Drink or Menu item	15	4,3	51,7
Location	15	4,3	56,0
Specific member of staff	13	3,7	59,8
Entertainment staff	10	2,9	62,6
General staff comment	9	2,6	65,2
Kids club/park	9	2,6	67,8
the word "honeymoon"	9	2,6	70,4
Environment feature	8	2,3	72,7
Other	8	2,3	75,0
Personal or Butler service	7	2,0	77,0
Entertainment	7	2,0	79,0
F&B Options-Choice	6	1,7	80,7
Room Service	6	1,7	82,5
Arrival comment	6	1,7	84,2
In-room Mini Bar	6	1,7	85,9
Other room feature	6	1,7	87,6
Activity	6	1,7	89,4
Excursion	5	1,4	90,8
SPA	4	1,1	92,0
Other holiday description	4	1,1	93,1
Comment on staff attitude	3	0,9	94,0
Service Level description	3	0,9	94,8
Sports & Watersports	3	0,9	95,7
Other Facility	3	0,9	96,6
Pillow Menu	3	0,9	97,4
Comment on design	3	0,9	98,3
Patisserie	2	0,6	98,9
Other Service	2	0,6	99,4
Other room amenity	2	0,6	100
Total	348	100	

As Table 3 shows, the most commonly used phrases in hotel reviews concerned Restaurant and Bar outlets, Room types or descriptive characteristics of these, mentions of Pool and Waterslide facilities and phrases referring to the hotels' Locations. Items regarding the resorts' restaurants appeared in 79 of the phrases, out of which 18 referred to the hotels main buffet restaurant and 61 named or described additional restaurant outlets within the hotels. Furthermore, 14 of the 348 most frequently appearing phrases mentioned Food, Drinks or Menu items such as "lobster", "ice-cream" and "branded drinks" and 5 additional phrases were comments regarding available F&B choices, such as "choice of restaurants" and "food choice".

Out of 32 items (9.2%) associated with hotel staff, specific staff members of the hotels were named in the top mentioned phrases 13 times, while 10 phrases out of 32 regarded "entertainment staff". It can be illustrated clearer on Table 4 which presents a grouping of the above categories in the general hotel areas they refer to, that phrases regarding provided Services (e.g. "room service", "personal butler", "beach service") or a description of the level of these (eg "little touches"), appeared 26 times in total, followed by items describing Room features or amenities which appeared in 17 (4.9%) of the phrases analyzed.

Table 4: Categories of most frequently used phrases in Tripadvisor.com’s top 25 AI hotels’ reviews – Grouped by general hotel area

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Food & Beverage	132	37,9	37,9
Facility	39	11,2	49,1
Room Type	35	10,1	59,2
Staff	32	9,2	68,4
Service	26	7,5	75,9
Room feature or amenity	17	4,9	80,7
Location	15	4,3	85,1
Holiday description	14	4,0	89,1
Entertainment or Activity	12	3,4	92,5
Other	10	2,9	95,4
Environment feature	8	2,3	97,7
Excursion	5	1,4	99,1
Design feature	3	0,9	100,0
Total	348	100,0	

Phrases regarding Food & Beverage offerings were by far the most frequently appearing in reviews of these hotels. All 23 hotels which finally entered the analysis had at least one F&B item in their 17 most frequently mentioned words/phrases, while most had multiple concerning F&B offerings or descriptions of these.

Out of 39 items associated with resorts’ facilities, 21 concerned Swimming Pools or Waterslide facilities. Phrases referring to Room types guests stayed in or their view descriptions such as “junior suite” and “sea view” appeared in 35 phrases in total. Interestingly, out of 13 phrases identified as a description of the holiday (e.g. “great holiday”), 9 of these included the word “honeymoon”.

3.2 Stage 2 Results

Each of the 52 items is presented by descending mean score in Table 5, categorised into three groups according to their mean score of willingness-to-accept a higher price if included.

Table 5: Questionnaire Items – Willingness to accept a higher price

Item Scores - Willingness to accept a higher price if included				
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation
1	Arrival and Departure transfer	5,16	133	1,784
2	3 to 5 Restaurants	5,01	138	1,726
3	Sauna, steam bath and jacuzzi access	4,89	121	2,012
4	Massage,spa,beauty treatments (90min)	4,73	122	1,887
5	King-size bed	4,72	129	1,971
6	Freshly squeezed fruit juices	4,66	132	2,053
7	Local excursion	4,65	127	1,935
8	Massage,spa,beauty treatments (unlimited)	4,62	122	2,044
9	Pool & Beach waiter service	4,59	132	1,915
10	No check-in or check-out times	4,58	126	1,994
11	Dine-out Experience	4,49	126	1,913
12	6 or more restaurants	4,37	133	2,071
13	Michelin starred chefs	4,31	131	2,171
14	Chef's Table experience	4,29	129	2,003
15	No reservation required (for restaurants)	4,22	129	1,946
16	Branded Drinks	4,17	138	2,018
17	Green Certification	4,16	116	1,956
18	One hair treatment	4,13	121	2,109
19	In-room mini bar (stocked, replenished)	4,09	128	2,036
20	Introductory scuba lessons	4,08	122	2,141
21	Motorised watersports (unlimited)	4,06	122	2,085
22	Premium Drinks	4,05	136	2,047
23	Motorised watersports (2 rounds)	4,05	125	1,990
24	Espresso Machine	4,05	130	2,033
25	Luxury international branded bathroom amenities	4,02	128	2,092
26	Airport Lounge at departure	3,99	126	2,180
27	Bands or DJ's	3,98	127	2,113
28	Private chauffeured transfer	3,98	125	2,153
29	Room service (limited)	3,97	132	2,065
30	Cooking,dancing,diving,fishing,mixology or language lessons	3,97	123	2,005
31	Branded coffe/tea	3,92	138	2,132
32	International Beer	3,88	133	2,008
33	Pillow Menu	3,87	126	1,869
34	Unlimited scuba diving	3,84	121	2,133
35	Complimentary laundry	3,82	123	2,024
36	No wristbands	3,82	117	2,028
37	Late night restaurant	3,82	126	2,133
38	French Champagne	3,79	134	2,186
39	Professional Fitness classes	3,76	121	2,089
40	Stay at one - play at two	3,67	122	1,996
41	Room service (24h)	3,64	128	2,119
42	Branded Ice-cream	3,64	136	1,986
43	500 euro resort credit towards spa,excursions,private diners	3,63	122	2,064
44	Executive Club lounge access at resort	3,59	120	2,077
45	Personal trainer	3,5	122	2,167
46	Free wedding ceremony	3,44	119	2,141
47	Smartphone/tablet with data package	3,23	122	2,214
48	Butler or personal assistant	3,22	130	2,091
49	Babysitting	3,22	120	2,147
50	500 euro resort credit towards wedding ceremony	3,16	117	2,099
51	Golf rounds	3,14	122	1,974
52	Calls abroad	2,99	123	2,132

“Arrival/departure transfer” and “access to sauna, steam bath and Jacuzzi” are often included in hotel packages regardless of whether they operate on an AI board basis. It appears from Table 5 that these two items are also strongly valued inclusions for AI guests, ranking no1 and no3 respectively. The choice of 3-5 restaurants in the resort for lunch and dinner ranked between the two aforementioned items and appears influential to the selling price of an AI package, while the inclusion of “freshly squeezed fruit juices” ranked as the next most desired “Food & Beverage” item of those included in the questionnaire.

Both the provisions of 90 minutes as well as unlimited “Massage, spa or beauty treatments” were ranked highly by guests, along with the inclusions of Pool & Beach waiter service and the ability to Check-in or Check-out of the room with no time restrictions.

Furthermore, a WTP for the inclusion of activities outside of the resort is indicated by the research findings with “At least one local excursion” averaging 4,65 out of 7 and a “Dine-out experience” scoring 4,49. On the other hand, the option to enjoy a 2nd hotel’s facilities within the package (“stay at one play at two”) does not seem to be such an attractive motivator for AI guests.

It should be noted that the two general hotel room characteristics included in the questionnaire, which were discussed in the methodology section, ranked 5th (king sized bed) and 33rd (“pillow menu”). In terms of the categorisation used in the questionnaire, the highest WTP was displayed for “Transfer Services” with a mean score of 4,46, followed by “F&B” and ‘Rooms’ which both averaged 4,14.

The findings from the analysis of questions 53 and 54 are presented in Table 6

Table 6: “Most strongly valued if included” item counts and supplement values

	Item List	N	Percent	Total Percent	Minimum supplement	Average Supplement (€ prpd)	Maximum supplement (€ prpd)	Range
1	6 or more restaurants	20	7,63	20,41	0,00	19,41	50,00	50
2	Arrival and Departure transfer	17	6,49	17,35	0,00	18,77	50,00	50
3	No check-in or check-out times	16	6,11	16,33	0,00	20,54	50,00	50
4	Massage,spa,beauty treatments (unlimited)	11	4,20	11,22	4,00	24,89	50,00	46
5	Dine-out Experience	11	4,20	11,22	0,00	21,50	100,00	100
6	King-size bed	11	4,20	11,22	0,00	11,89	25,00	25
7	Massage,spa,beauty treatments (90min)	9	3,44	9,18	20,00	27,86	50,00	30
8	3 to 5 Restaurants	9	3,44	9,18	0,00	21,43	75,00	75
9	Local excursion	9	3,44	9,18	4,00	14,25	30,00	26
10	Freshly squeezed fruit juices	9	3,44	9,18	1,00	8,88	20,00	19
11	Motorised watersports (unlimited)	8	3,05	8,16	5,00	20,63	40,00	35
12	Michelin starred chefs	7	2,67	7,14	4,00	29,00	55,00	51
13	Espresso Machine	7	2,67	7,14	0,00	10,00	20,00	20
14	Branded Drinks	7	2,67	7,14	0,00	8,14	20,00	20
15	Introductory scuba lessons	6	2,29	6,12	10,00	43,33	90,00	80
16	Premium Drinks	6	2,29	6,12	20,00	22,50	30,00	10
17	Green Certification	6	2,29	6,12	3,00	14,60	40,00	37
18	Sauna, steam bath and jacuzzi access	6	2,29	6,12	0,00	11,25	30,00	30
19	No reservations required (for restaurants)	6	2,29	6,12	0,00	2,50	10,00	10
20	Private chauffeured transfer	5	1,91	5,10	2,00	12,20	40,00	38
21	Professional Fitness classes	5	1,91	5,10	0,00	10,00	30,00	30
22	Pool & Beach waiter service	5	1,91	5,10	2,00	9,40	20,00	18
23	Pillow Menu	5	1,91	5,10	0,00	3,50	9,00	9
24	500 euro resort credit towards spa,excursions,private dinners	4	1,53	4,08	30,00	36,67	50,00	20
25	Executive Club lounge access at resort	4	1,53	4,08	10,00	18,33	30,00	20
26	Motorised watersports (2 rounds)	4	1,53	4,08	10,00	16,67	30,00	20
27	One hair treatment	4	1,53	4,08	3,00	12,67	20,00	17
28	Room service (24h)	4	1,53	4,08	2,00	10,67	20,00	18
29	Bands or DJ's	3	1,15	3,06	10,00	36,67	80,00	70
30	Stay at one - play at two	3	1,15	3,06	20,00	28,33	35,00	15
31	Babysitting	3	1,15	3,06	10,00	23,33	40,00	30
32	Personal trainer	3	1,15	3,06	10,00	16,67	20,00	10
33	International Beer	3	1,15	3,06	3,00	11,50	20,00	17
34	Branded coffe/tea	3	1,15	3,06	10,00	10,00	10,00	0
35	Cooking,dancing,diving,fishing,mixology or language lessons	3	1,15	3,06	0,00	8,33	20,00	20
36	Branded Ice-cream	3	1,15	3,06	2,00	4,00	5,00	3
37	In-room mini bar (stocked, replenished)	3	1,15	3,06	0,00	1,00	2,00	2
38	Late night restaurant	2	0,76	2,04	55,00	55,00	55,00	0
39	Chef's Table experience	2	0,76	2,04	10,00	30,00	50,00	40
40	Smartphone/tablet with data package	2	0,76	2,04	20,00	20,00	20,00	0
41	No wristbands	2	0,76	2,04				
42	Luxury international branded bathroom amenities	1	0,38	1,02	50,00	50,00	50,00	0
43	Unlimited scuba diving	1	0,38	1,02	40,00	40,00	40,00	0
44	Airport Lounge at departure	1	0,38	1,02	3,00	3,00	3,00	0
45	Complimentary laundry	1	0,38	1,02	3,00	3,00	3,00	0
46	Free wedding ceremony	1	0,38	1,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
47	Calls abroad	1	0,38	1,02				
	Total	262	100,00	267,35				

Over 20% of respondents chose “6 or more restaurants” in the resort in their top-three valued inclusions, followed by “arrival and departure transfer” and “no check-in/check-out times”. The provisions of a “dine-out experience”, “king-size bed” and unlimited “massage,

spa or beauty treatments” ranked fourth in counts and were each chosen by 11 respondents.

Furthermore, while certain items appeared in the top-three inclusions, some respondents assigned a zero supplement to these, signifying a high importance but low willingness-to-pay a higher price. As illustrated in Table 7, while six guests selected “no reservations required” in their top-3 valued items, three of these reported they would not be Willing To Pay extra for this item,, The means stores of the categories under which the survey items were grouped in the questionnaire is presented in Table 8.

Table 7: Most Strongly Valued” items with “Zero” Willingness to Pay

Frequency Table				
Item List	"0" Supplement cases	Total cases	Percent	Supplement mean (€)
No reservations required	3	6	50,00%	2,50
Professional Fitness classes	2	5	40,00%	10,00
Pillow Menu	2	5	40,00%	3,50
Sauna, steam bath and jacuzzi access	2	6	33,33%	11,25
Cooking,dancing,diving,fishing,mixology or language lessons	1	3	33,33%	8,33
In-room mini bar (stocked, replenished)	1	3	33,33%	1,00
Branded Drinks	1	7	14,29%	8,14
Espresso Machine	1	7	14,29%	10,00
Arrival and Departure transfer	2	17	11,76%	18,77
3 to 5 Restaurants	1	9	11,11%	21,43

Table 8: Willingness to accept a higher price - Survey Categories

Survey Categories			
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Transfer Services	4,46	135	1,830
Food & Beverage Items	4,19	141	1,565
Hotel Room Items	4,19	134	1,673
Spa Beauty & Weddings	4,16	123	1,662
Activities / Entertainment	3,98	135	1,652
Various	3,98	127	1,631
Personalised Services	3,76	132	1,726
Communication Services	3,10	124	2,094
Valid N (listwise)		120	

Additional Items

The final question of the survey requested respondents to cite any further elements beyond the fifty-two items listed, which guests would consider valuable if included in their AI package. Although some of the responses were not limited to package inclusions and referred to facilities (“heated pool”) or policies (“pets allowed”), no items were omitted from the list presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Additional elements beyond the survey items

Additional elements	
24h maid service	Organic food
Personnel speaking own language	Beer kegs at tables
Extra beach towels	Fine dining experience
Car Hire	Original Coca cola
Paddling boards	Lunch box for excursions
Hiking	Greek corners (local food)
Beach parties	Locally themed restaurant
Top tier daily shows and events	No time restrictions on drinks (24h AI)
Yacht trip/boat excursion	More local experiences and brands
Bottled water	Heated pool
Branded water	Resort map
Daily bottled water in room	In-room Safebox
Champagne bar	Adult only zones
Ice-poles for children	British TV channels
Larger selection in drinks	Pets allowed

As is depicted in the above list, fifteen of the additional items mentioned concerned F&B offerings, three items mentioned “Local” food or experiences while five items concerned resort services. It should be noted that “Car Hire” and “British TV channels” were mentioned twice, while a reference to bottled water was made by three respondents.

4. DISCUSSION

This work is one of the first studies in the tourism literature that explores consumer perceptions of Ultra AI resorts and preferences towards their services. Through a two-stage approach, this study provides an exploratory understanding of various drivers of customers perceived value of Ultra AI resorts, advancing the AI literature.

First, we make a methodological contribution in that respondents' stated WTP is often not alone sufficient to establish actual behavior (Breidert et al., 2006). While certain attributes may in theory affect guests' WTP for an AI package, the success of its application in each resort is usually portrayed in their quality performance and "electronic word-of-mouth", which indirectly affects guests WTP for the resort (Kim et al., 2017; Phillips et al., 2017). In order to account for both "stated" and "revealed" WTP, our findings must be interpreted taking both the performance and importance dimensions into consideration.

The review of the top-performing AI resorts worldwide on Tripadvisor.com reveals certain commonalities among leading AI resorts. A predominant determinant of the success of these resorts lies in their Food & Beverage offerings, which also appear to have a major potential to promote e-word-of-mouth. Each of the top-25 resorts examined, primarily met or surpassed customer F&B expectations, while most hotels also achieved recurring positive comments regarding their facilities, rooms, staff and service. While previous literature regarding online reviews of hotels in general suggests that Staff, Service and Hotel Rooms are the strongest motivators of positive reviews (Barreda & Bilgihan, 2013), it becomes evident that AI resort customers predominantly address F&B and Facilities in their positive online reviews, which may imply that the importance of these aspects is stronger for AI guests.

The analysis of the survey results highlights several areas which appear to increase guests' willingness-to-pay for a higher priced AI resort. One of the most interesting findings is the high WTP for the inclusion of at least 90 min of "massage, spa & beauty treatments", as this offering seems to currently remain excluded from most all-inclusive resort packages and may

signify an opportunity for a value-adding element. While transfer services are also very highly valued, this inclusion is very often purchased and offered by tour operators as well.

Contrary to generic hotel research that predominantly highlights various other hotel attributes such as location, hotel rooms, staff and service quality, the study's findings strongly suggest that F&B offerings are of utmost importance for AI Resorts and the foundation on which the success of the top-performing resorts on Tripadvisor is based. Moreover, guests of typical AI Resorts indicated a high WTP for additional F&B inclusions, especially the availability of numerous restaurants in the package, including a dine-out experience outside the resort. Considering dine-out experiences are not currently offered by many Ultra AI hotels nor has a measurement of their value been included in previous studies of AI guests, this finding seems potentially very impactful. If the implied WTP for this inclusion is indeed such that allows resorts food cost budget to rise to a level at which covering guest meals at external restaurants is viable, the potential to further expand the market and change existing perception of non-AI travellers towards these resorts is understandably vast.

The study confirms the value of including departure & arrival transfers and indicates that guests appear prepared to accept a higher priced resort for the inclusion of at least one excursion and the convenience of having no check-in or check-out times. Therefore, the possibility for inclusion of these elements in Ultra AI resorts should be examined by hotel managers. These important inclusions for AI guests have not been present in many past studies on hotel attributes (Wen, 2010; Kim et al., 2017).

Of high significance is the implied willingness of guests to pay the inclusion of massage, spa and beauty treatments, since this inclusion has not yet been adopted widely by AI Resorts and also not particularly examined in AI research (Corona, 2014). While it seems unlimited treatments are a strong value-adding inclusion, the provision of 90minutes towards free treatments appears itself both highly valued and capable of providing differentiating power to resorts which offer it. On the other hand, while sauna, steam bath and jacuzzi access seem to be

strongly preferred by guests, its lower ranking amongst “most-valued items” may imply this item is somewhat expected from AI Resorts already. These findings seem to support prior research which suggests that not only is wellness becoming a key trend in the hospitality sector but that the absence of wellness attributes may lead to discontent (Park et al., 2021). Based on the results of this study, hotel managers should also consider including beauty and spa services in the formation of their Ultra AI packages.

While the results of the guests’ WTP for the 52 items highlighted important attributes for AI travellers, it was made apparent through the review of previous studies that a multiple evaluation of attributes would be necessary to differentiate important from distinguishing attributes on the choice of purchasing a higher priced AI package (Jones & Chen, 2011). Indeed, by additionally requesting respondents to state the three most strongly valued attributes that could be included in their package, this study was able to provide a more comprehensive understanding of guests’ preferences for AI package attributes.

It is evident by the responses of the initial evaluation of WTP for the 52 items measured that guests considered that “unlimited” use of an item would carry a higher supplement than limited offerings thus incorporating an “importance” dimension into their responses, ranking “3-5 Restaurants” higher in WTP than “6 or more Restaurants” and “90 min of beauty treatments” higher than “unlimited treatments”. It can be therefore assumed that guests would strongly value the inclusion of 3-5 restaurants and 90 minutes of beauty treatments, however, once these items are included the likelihood of accepting a higher supplement for more restaurants or unlimited treatments is slightly lower. On the other hand, when stating the three most valued inclusions without considering a price trade-off, “6 or more restaurants” appeared as the most preferred element of all and all unlimited elements such as beauty treatments, motorized watersports and premium spirits ranked higher than restrictive elements such as “90 minutes”, “two rounds” and “branded spirits”, respectively.

By combining alternate evaluations in the survey, the study pointed out several items

which seemed to be considered highly valuable by guests but exhibited a low indicated monetary supplement or a lower numbers of counts as a “most valued” inclusion. The managerial implication deriving from this is that highly valued items that exhibited low distinguishing power may soon become “expected” by guests and their inclusion may be regarded as standard. Furthermore, the study also identified factors beyond the list of current Ultra AI inclusions which may be of value to guests and could be taken into consideration in future Ultra AI package design, considering the rapid evolution associated with the AI business model (Anderson, 2010).

Table 10: Implications for future AI – Ultra AI development

May become <i>expected</i> in Standard AI	May be worth <i>including</i> in Ultra AI
Sauna, steam bath and jacuzzi access	Car hire
Pool & Beach waiter service	24h maid service
In-room mini bar (stocked, replenished)	Boat excursions
Luxury international branded bathroom amenities	Lunch Boxes
3 to 5 Restaurants	Locally themed resturants
	Organically sourced food

With the addition of **branded bottle water** which also seems to be already included in Ultra AI resorts, the relevant new AI package elements deriving from the final, open-ended question of the survey are presented in Table 10. It should be noted that Lunch-boxes don’t seem to be an exclusive characteristic of Ultra AI resorts but are neither a standard inclusion in typical AI packages.

In evaluating the recommendations of this study’s findings, managers need to be aware of all possible risks associated with each item before adopting them in their packages. For example, the inclusion of certain attributes such as “dine-out” options and “lunch-boxes” may carry increased health & safety risks which need to be considered and addressed.

4.1 Limitations & Avenues for further research

While the questionnaire was completed by guests of 17 nationalities, it should be noted that the island of Rhodes is not a popular golf destination, therefore it appears reasonable that guests visiting the island were not primarily interested in this attribute. Consequently, to examine the validity of the results in destinations with dissimilar characteristics, a sample of respondents in resorts of such destinations would be necessary. Similarly, since the AI model also exists beyond beach resorts, further research on other forms of AI travel such as ship cruises may yield different results.

Furthermore, as the sample was not large enough to allow statistical analysis of demographic differences, further research would be useful in providing a greater understanding of variance and highlight attributes of focus for resorts emphasizing on certain target groups.

Considering the AI model's continuous evolution (Issa & Jayawardena, 2003; Crocker, 2017), the distinguishing value and WTP for each of the fifty-two included attributes will most likely change in coming years and a re-evaluation of these will be necessary. Moreover, the items included in the questionnaire were restricted to package elements and deliberately ignored other distinguishing features such as hotel facilities, location and room features, apart from the exceptions mentioned in the methodology section.

Following on the research findings which indicated a relative ranking of value and a monetary range of WTP measured independently for each of the fifty-two attributes, a smaller number of attributes could be further tested in pricing scenarios using discrete choice analysis, as a more accurate method of predicting real purchase behavior (Bredert et al, 2006).

5. CONCLUSION

The study attempted to fill the gap that exists in literature regarding Standard and Ultra AI packages and measure the value of Ultra AI offerings. Considering methodological suggestions of previous work on hospitality literature, the study measured the perceived value of each attribute rather than its direct effect on hotel selection, through thorough analysis of both primary and secondary data.

A multi-dimensional methodology was adopted aiming to combine a customers' attitude metric with a hotel performance dimension, to account for the trade-off that naturally occurs in purchasing and to also differentiate between expected attributes and those with higher distinguishing power. It is evident from this study's findings that singular evaluations of guests' stated WTP are often not enough to establish a clear picture of actual WTP.

In addition, the content analysis performed on reviews of the leading AI Resorts on Tripadvisor.com captured the indirect influence of customer satisfaction and added a *post-purchase* understanding of perceived value of the resorts' attributes, complementing the survey instrument which was handed to guests *during* their holiday but also included questions regarding *future* choice.

By targeting spend on inclusions that are valued by guests, resort managers may respond to their growing expectations and achieve differentiation from the increasing competition in the AI industry, while maintaining the cost leadership advantages associated with the AI business model. In addition, the suggestions regarding items which may be or may become expected by guests in the future along with possible additional inclusions, may assist Ultra AI resorts in possibly evolving the model further and should be included in future research on AI hotel attributes. Furthermore, hotel owners/managers may benefit from considering the inclusions in the formation of future Ultra AI packages.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Survey Nationality Sample Analysis

Sample Analysis - Nationality Group Report				
		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	British	33	26,2	26,2
	French	21	16,7	42,9
	Scandinavian	19	15,1	57,9
	German	13	10,3	68,3
	Finnish	9	7,1	75,4
	Greek	8	6,3	81,7
	Poland	6	4,8	86,5
	Belgium	4	3,2	89,7
	Russian & ex-USSR	3	2,4	92,1
	Italian	3	2,4	94,4
	Netherlands	2	1,6	96,0
	Marocco	1	0,8	96,8
	Slovenian	1	0,8	97,6
	Canadian	1	0,8	98,4
	Indian	1	0,8	99,2
Swiss	1	0,8	100,0	
	Total	126	100,0	
Missing	System	15		
Total		141		